

An empirical investigation on the benefits of gamification in programming courses

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Context: Programming courses are compulsory on most Engineering degrees, but students' performance on these courses is often not as good as expected. Programming is difficult for students to learn, given that it includes a lot of new, complex and abstract topics. All of this has led experts to the conclusion that new teaching techniques are required if students are to be motivated and engaged in learning on programming courses. Gamification has come to be an effective technique in education in general, and is especially useful on programming courses. This motivated us to develop an open-source gamified platform, called UDPiler, for use on a programming course.

Objective: The main goal of this paper is to obtain empirical evidence on the improvement of students' learning performance when using UDPiler in comparison to a non-gamified compiler.

Method: A quasi-experiment was performed with two groups of first-year Engineering students at the Diego Portales University in Chile, using a non-gamified compiler and a gamified platform, respectively.

Results: The results reveal that the students obtained better marks when the gamified platform was used to learn C programming. In addition, there is statistical significance in favor of there being a positive effect on the learning performance of those students who used the gamified platform.

Conclusions: The results allow us to conclude that gamification is an encouraging approach with which to teach C programming, a finding which is aligned with previous empirical studies concerning gamification on programming courses, carried out in academic contexts. Nonetheless, we are aware that further validation is also required to corroborate and strengthen the findings obtained and to investigate whether the kind of gamified elements (mechanics, dynamics and aesthetics) used have any influence on students' performance, among other issues that deserve further investigation and which are explained throughout this paper.

CCS → General and reference → Cross-computing tools and techniques → **Empirical studies**; Social and professional topics → Professional topics → Computing education → Computing education programs → **Computational science and engineering education**

Keywords: Gamification; undergraduate education; quasi-experiment, programming courses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Programming courses are the first step in many Engineering degrees, since they help students to understand the abstraction of problems. These courses are focused on teaching how to abstract problems and provide solutions by structuring a set of variables, control instructions, and functions; i.e., programming courses concentrate on opening students' minds, thus enabling them to produce the algorithms needed to attain an efficient computational solution. Nonetheless,

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programming is a difficult subject for first-year students to learn [1], given that it includes a lot of new, complex and abstract topics, and that it also requires logical/mathematical thinking.

In 2013, and after several years of being involved in programming courses at the Diego Portales University (Chile), some of the authors of this paper observed that students are not very motivated while studying the programming content of degree courses. This is reflected in the small amount of time they spend on performing exercises, in addition to the consequently low grades obtained. These issues have also been extensively reported in literature [2], [3]. Moreover, in many cases this lack of motivation is reflected in the high dropout rates of students on programming courses [4], [5].

The problems outlined above have concerned educators for decades; great efforts have thus been made by researchers and educators in their quest to overcome the difficulties encountered when teaching programming. The use of serious games, which provide novice programmers with interactive and entertaining experiences, is one method that is currently being explored. The various literature reviews that have recently appeared generally reveal positive outcomes as regards game-based learning [6], [7] and particularly highlight the usefulness of serious games when teaching programming [3].

While games designed specifically for educational purposes have been used for decades, interest in using gaming elements in non-game applications has recently grown in an attempt to increase engagement with products and services [8]. The main idea behind this is to transfer the motivational power of videogames to other processes by encouraging users to persevere and to tolerate the challenges of their quests more successfully. The use of design elements that are characteristic of games in non-game contexts is defined as gamification [9]. Gamification can take different forms, and includes aspects such as social competition, or the incentivizing of behavior through the use of badges and a reward system [10].

Gamification relies on the argument that many traditional activities (including school activities and traditional learning) are not inherently interesting, while games, and especially computer-games, are “fun”. Introducing game-like features into these otherwise dull activities would, therefore, make them more attractive [11], [12]. There are a considerable number of expectations as regards their usefulness in teaching, and particularly the teaching of programming. Evidence reveals that gamification has been successfully employed in teachers’ efforts to engage students and has managed to increase their motivation in the learning process [13], [14], [15], [16]. There is, however, still a lack of rigorous empirical research that would demonstrate whether the motivation and engagement gained thanks to gamification do, in fact, contribute to the effectiveness of the learning process [17]. In particular, the works presented in [18], [19], and [20] show evidence of some weaknesses when reporting on game-based learning in

engineering education; these include small sample sizes and the lack of comparison groups that would enable an assessment of the learning effects, which hinders replication and the possibility of generalizing the results obtained.

All of the above considerations have led us to develop an open-source gamified platform called “UDPiler” [21], which was designed in order to teach C programming at the Diego Portales University and carry out empirical research into the benefits of using this platform in comparison to a non-gamified compiler. The aim was to address the methodological limitations mentioned in the previous paragraph, which are also reported in literature. To this end, we carried out a quasi-experiment with first-year students on programming courses at the Diego Portales University. The main goal of this quasi-experiment was to study how effectively students learn the C programming language when using a gamified platform in comparison to using a non-gamified platform that employs traditional techniques. At this point, it is important to clarify that we focus our study in the set of concepts of the C programming language that are part of the contents of the first-year programming course (described in section 4.2) at the Diego Portales University, since many other concepts of C are not taught on this course.

The quasi-experiment was run with two groups of first-year students on a programming course, in two consecutive years: 410 students who used the gamified platform in 2015 compared to 407 students who used the non-gamified platform.

The main contribution of this paper is the empirical evidence obtained by means of the quasi-experiment, which shows statistical significance to the effect that gamification is effective as regards improving the learning of the C programming language on first-year programming courses.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 outlines some relevant related work concerning the use of gamification on programming courses. In Section 3, the main characteristics of the UDPiler gamified platform are presented. Section 4 provides a detailed description of the quasi-experiment, and Section 5 presents an overall analysis and discussion of the results obtained, along with the threats to the validity of the quasi-experiment. Finally, Section 6 provides our conclusions and details of our future work.

2 Related Work

Gamification has been widely-studied when applied to education, as can be observed in the following literature reviews [13], [14], [15], [16], [18], [3]. These literature reviews reveal that gamification in education is growing in importance, mainly at university level. This result is not surprising if we consider the complexity of the courses at universities and the characteristics of 21st century university students [22].

With regard to teaching on programming courses, which is the main focus of the research presented in the current paper, the following lines provide a summary of existing literature concerning gamified platforms that attempt to engage students in the learning of programming (see Table 1). Lehtonen et al. [23], present a gamified platform called Javala, which is used to learn Java starting from C++. In this work, the goal was to evaluate the role of gamification in an online learning environment called Javala; the results showed that, on average, the users who had the gamification features both used the environment for longer and completed more exercises than the users who did not use gamification. However, this work was performed without using a rigorous empirical study, signifying that it is difficult to replicate the findings.

An experiment with two sections of 32 subjects was performed by Dubois et al. to evaluate the Sonar tool [24], which is used to implement a board-game in Java. The goal of this study was to investigate ad-hoc gamification mechanisms for software development which depend on the behavior to be incentivized. The variables in this work were clearly defined, such as LOC, the percentage of Sonar rule compliance or the percentages of branch coverage of test cases, code duplication and javaDoc documentation, respectively. The results show a significant increase in the quality of the software artifacts produced with the gamification approach when compared to the quantity of the artifacts produced without the gamification approach. Nevertheless, the small number of subjects who participated makes it difficult to ensure that these results are reliable.

Paiva et al. [28] present Enki, which is a web-based IDE used in the Introduction to C# Programming. Enki provides an e-learning component that allows documentation to be provided to students; it has a repository containing the learning objects, an educational sequencing service that allows students to learn at different rhythms, and a gamified console that enables students to obtain points when they do an exercise correctly. This IDE was evaluated in relation to its acceptance by using an experiment with 70 students, and a survey was later applied to 25 students. There are no details about the experiment performed, i.e., the comparison of the gamified IDE with a non-gamified IDE, the variables measured, and the results obtained are not provided in this work. With regard to the results of the survey, the majority of the students (56%) classified Enki as quite a good tool, while many of them (40%) stated that Enki was a good or a very good tool. Very few students (4%) found it either bad or very bad. However, an analysis of the gamification aspects of this IDE was not performed, signifying that it is not possible to infer whether the usefulness of Enki is a direct benefit of gamification.

Piccioni et al. [29] applied gamification on an introduction to programming course. The gamified platform corresponds to a Moodle that provides quizzes integrated into the online lectures, and a service infrastructure with which to develop and execute programs in the browser. The quizzes were gamified by rewarding students

with badges. In this work, a comparison between the gamified course and a traditional e-learning course was performed, focusing on the completion of the quizzes designed for this course. The results show that most of the students who answered five questionnaires (a total of 318 answers for various lectures, quizzes, and programming exercises) stated that the online lectures and quizzes were at exactly the right level of difficulty (84%) and that the programming exercises were at exactly the right level of difficulty (69%), but 23% of those surveyed considered that the programming exercises were too hard. A specific analysis of the learning performance on the gamified course was not, however, performed.

TRAKLA2 is a learning environment for algorithm simulation presented by Hakulinen et al. [25], which was evaluated by means of an experiment using a between-subject design with 278 subjects. The goal of this study was to reject the hypothesis that there are no significant differences in students' behaviour, judged by the difference between the number of badges earned by the treatment group and the amount gained by the control group. The authors evaluated this using the students' behavior when doing TRAKLA2 exercises, measured by time management, carefulness, and learning. These variables were calculated using the number of badges that the students won. The results of the study show that the majority of students behaved similarly in both the treatment and the control group (70% and 73% of the total points, respectively). Since different badges were assigned depending on the submission of exercises without errors, along with rapid submission, and on the relative complexity of the exercises, these authors concluded that it is necessary to evaluate each type of badge separately.

An anonymous survey of 162 students was performed by Haaranen et al. [26] to evaluate the A+ learning management system. The goal of this survey was to investigate whether students react to gamification features such as badges, and whether these have any positive or negative effects on their behavior. The results show that the authors in question did not observe any negative effects on learning results; the badges did not have any overall significant effect on the course results, or on students' behavior. However, this study lacks a definition as regards the variables used to measure the students' behavior in order to obtain these results. A similar case is the study presented by Grant et al. [27], which evaluates the effectiveness of the use of badges to motivate the use of the Stack Overflow platform (i.e., enforce behavior when using it), by using 40GB of logs containing the users' behavior and the number of badges won by those using the platform, but no empirical method regarding the performance of this study was provided, thus making it difficult to understand the context and to replicate it.

A gamified platform employed on a computer games development course was presented by O'Donovan et al. [2], whose goal was to evaluate positive and negative aspects of gamification on university level courses. This was done by carrying out a survey of 44 subjects to evaluate whether gamification improves students'

understanding, and whether it increases their engagement in the design of the course. The variables used to measure this goal were: perceived understanding, engagement, overall course mark, improvement by story and theme. The result obtained was that students are more motivated by progress bars than by the badges denoting some progress in skills. A greater amount of empirical studies are, therefore, needed to clarify the effects of using badges to improve students' behavior.

A robot game is presented by Shim et al.[31]; it is used to motivate learning on programming courses. An experiment was carried out with 48 students to evaluate the effectiveness of using the robot game. The results show that providing a game format motivates student learning, but there are some limitations in the study (such as the small number of subjects and the use of a questionnaire to evaluate the learning of programming concepts) that should be tackled in order to generate sound results concerning the effectiveness of gamification on programming courses.

The Clara framework is presented by Bogdanovich et al. [30]. This has gamified elements which are designed to motivate students to learn and to continuously improve their solutions. This framework, therefore, uses stars, badges, and challenges. The gamification of the Clara framework was evaluated with a total of 160 students (70 of whom used the Clara framework). The results provide evidence that gamification elements help students to obtain better solutions and that these elements had a positive impact on their academic performance. However, this study shows neither the strategy nor the statistical methods used to calculate academic performance.

To sum up, the related work described in this section reveals that the use of gamification techniques in learning processes has been widely-studied; this is particularly true in the case of gamification when applied to programming courses (see Table 1). These pieces of work focus mainly on the evaluation of how a game element (badges) affects students' behavior, rather than on the benefits of gamification for the learning process (see Table 1, third column). Despite the fact that students' behavior influences their learning, as is well-explained by Landers [32], the evidence of how great the improvement in learning has been is still an open question that has not been properly addressed by literature. We are of the opinion that an empirical investigation into the benefits of gamification is needed in order to engage universities in the use of gamified platforms. In this study we, therefore, contribute to this area by means of a rigorous empirical investigation into the benefits of gamification on programming courses. We also provide an open-source gamified platform called UDPiler with which to teach programming.

Table 1. Summary of empirical studies concerning gamification on programming courses

Ref.	Details of the study	Independent variables	Dependent variables	Results
[25]	A between-subjects design controlled experiment with 278 subjects	TRAKLA2 learning environment for algorithm simulation gamified with badges	Time management, carefulness and learning	Similar behavior in the control group and the experimental group; there is no significant change with the badges
[26]	An anonymous survey with 162 subjects, which consisted of 6 questions and a 5-point Likert scale.	A+ Learning environment gamified with badges	Learning, time management, carefulness	The use of badges does not have a significant (positive or negative) effect on the student's behavior.
[2]	A Survey of 44 subjects on a Computer games development course	Vula platform gamified with badges	Perceived understanding, engagement, overall course mark, improvement by story and theme.	Gamification improves students' understanding and their engagement.
[24]	Experiment: Two sections of 32 subjects, divided into groups of 2 or 3 students	Sonar tool gamified approach used to implement a board-game in Java	LOC, percentage of Sonar rules compliance, branch coverage of test cases, code duplication, and javaDoc documentation	A significant increase in the quality of the software artifacts of those subjects using the gamified approach.
[27]	Analysis of logs in stack overflow.	Stack Overflow gamified with badges	User behavior obtained in 40GB of logs	There is an increase in edits before the user wins a badge
[23]	Analysis of data collected in JAVALA	JAVALA platform gamified with points, badges and achievement announcements	Number of exercises solved, and time taken to solve the exercise.	Users that have gamification complete more exercises than users without gamification.
[28]	An experiment with 70 subjects was conducted on an Introduction to C# Programming course	Object: Enki web-based IDE gamified with leaderboards and rewards	Usefulness of Enki	The heuristics with the highest satisfaction were consistence, recognition and aesthetics, but speed, reliability, error prevention and help for users were deficient in Enki
[29]	Experiment with 273 subjects	SPOC (Small Private Online Course) with Moodle and quizzes gamified with badges	Online lectures seen, quizzes taken.	Students, on average, took quizzes almost five times more often than they viewed the online lectures, suggesting that the use of badges for correctly answered quizzes works.
[30]	Experiment with 160 subjects on a Programming Fundamentals course	“Clara” framework gamified with star ratings, badges and challenges, with user-created content	Increase in interest and motivation, academic performance	Evidence suggests that the inclusion of gamification helped students to produce better coding solutions and had a positive impact on academic performance

3 UDPiler: The Gamified compiler

UDPiler is a gamified platform that is used on first-year programming courses at the Engineering Faculty of Diego Portales University – Chile [33]. UDPiler is a platform that allows different programming challenges, such as the compiling of the C code or a review of the lecturer’s lessons, to be tackled; it also has a forum that enables questions to be addressed to the teacher.

UDPiler was developed using the MDA framework described in [34], which is composed of three elements: Mechanics, Dynamics and Aesthetics; the use of these components in conjunction allows the gamified platform to be designed, taking into account the viewpoints of the both developer and the player. The mechanics describe the components of the game, along with the representation of data and algorithms. The dynamics describe the run-time behavior of the mechanics, while the aesthetics correspond to the desirable emotional responses of the player, i.e., the elements that make a game fun.

3.1 Mechanics of UDPiler

UDPiler has 4 types of mechanics (challenges): multiple choice, completing or correcting a piece of code, writing a program, and winning a mini game by coding. The questions in UDPiler are grouped by topic, such as *Introduction to the C programming language*, and by concepts in each topic, such as *main*, *comments*, *libraries*, *conditions*, *cycles*, etc. An example of a challenge in which the students had to correct a piece of code is presented in Fig. 1.


```

1 #include <iostream>
2 using namespace std;
3
4 int main () {
5     cout << "MENU" << endl;
6     cout << "opcion 1. Imprimir A" << endl;
7     cout << "opcion 2. Imprimir B" << endl;
8     cout << "opcion 3. Imprimir C" << endl;
9
10    int opcion;
11    cin >> opcion;
12
13    if(opcion == 1)
14
15    if(opcion == 2)
16        cout << "0";
17    if(opcion == 3)
18        cout << "0";
19
20    return 0;
21 }

```

Fig. 1. Excerpt of coding in UDPiler

Each student that obtains a correct answer receives a medal and some points, which are added to a rank on the programming course. The medals are images with a related content, such as an image of a Marvel superhero with his/her official profile (provided by the official Marvel API), a top YouTube video, a mini game, and so on. Fig.2 shows an excerpt from the medals obtained by a student who used UDPiler.

Fig.2. Excerpt from a UDPiler student's collection of medals

In addition to the challenges, the gamified platform contains each student's ranking in comparison to that of other students on the programming course. This ranking is created with the points obtained by the students when they confront a challenge correctly. The student obtains 13 points for each challenge that is correctly confronted, regardless of its level of difficulty.

If the students successfully confront any of the mechanics mentioned above in the 4 different types of challenges, then their prize is the possibility of accessing specific online material and short video lessons focusing on special contents of the topics, such as sorting and searching algorithms, and others.

In summary, the gamified elements used by UDPiler are points, medals, a leaderboard and keys to unlock short video lessons or specific contents.

The non-gamification elements can, therefore, only be accessed by using the gamified elements, thus evidencing the relevance of gamification and, therefore, supporting the fact that gamification matters.

In a nutshell, the main modules of the UDPiler platform that support the mechanics presented above are the following (see Fig. 3):

Fig.3.UDPiler architecture

- **User management:** This module allows users to register on the platform using social network profiles, internal university accounts and email accounts such as Gmail. It also associates each user with their corresponding Student ID by means of their university accounts.
- **Player Management,** which allows a player profile to be assigned to a user account. The player profile is the main profile, and includes the rewards, scores and mini-game profiles that are associated with the player profile.
- **Challenge Module.** This module presents the challenges of the platform. Each topic is composed of sub-topics, and each sub-topic is composed of a set of challenges. As described previously, a Challenge can be multiple choice, or it might be to complete or correct a piece of code, carry out codification to produce an expected output (i.e., writing a program), or win a mini game by means of coding.
- **Rewards module.** This module is composed of a ranking module and a medal module. The ranking can generate several types of ranks: a simple ranking of points, a fury rank (points won during the previous week) and other kinds of ranks inspired by games.
- **The medal modules** provide several types of medals; each type of medal is associated with a type of content. For example, the *Captain America medal* is associated with the *Marvel API*; this means that there is a *Marvel medals* type. Other types of medals include YouTube videos, Vimeo videos, Wikipedia links, PokemonAPI, and Anime encyclopedia API.
- **Clans Module.** The team module allows players to create groups, called “clans”. There is a clan ranking, and a clan reward stock. Each clan rank comprises the average of the members’ points, and the reward stock is the result of adding up all the rewards that each clan member has obtained. Players can access the contents of the clans’ rewards.
- **Compiler Module.** The compiler module is in charge of retrieving C code, compiling it, and testing it with a pre-defined set of inputs and outputs. If the testing fails, a set of errors and warnings are prepared and sent back to the

player. If the testing is successful, the compiler module notifies the Ranks module, the Rewards module and the Challenges module.

The most frequently used controller of UDPiler is the *Playbox*, which allows the students to access the challenges by answering questions, correcting a piece of code or writing a program in order to obtain points, rewards and video lessons. In other words, the Playbox allows students to interact with the gamified elements of UDPiler.

3.2 Dynamics of UDPiler

The dynamics of UDPiler correspond to the execution of the modules described above. Each student enrolled on the programming course is, therefore, registered in UDPiler and consequently receives a single identification and a password that allows him/her to use the gamified platform.

When the students enter UDPiler, they can answer the questions by topics, look at the medals and videos won previously, see where they are located in the ranking, use the compiler, or simply go over the lecturer's lessons.

With regard to the UDPiler challenges, the students can solve them in the order that they want, for example, answer the most difficult questions first.

3.3 Aesthetics of UDPiler

There are 8 aspects [34] that are related to the aesthetics of gamified platforms, i.e., that have to do with the player's desirable emotional response: (1) *Sensation*: Game as sense of pleasure, (2) *Fantasy*: Game as make-believe, (3) *Narrative*: Game as drama, (4) *Challenge*: Game as an obstacle course, (5) *Fellowship*: Game as a social framework, (6) *Discovery*: Game as uncharted territory, (7) *Expression*: Game as self-discovery, and (8) *Submission*: Game as a pastime.

Many studies have designed and evaluated different incentive mechanisms in order to improve participation in learning networks; for example, some authors [35] give rewards according to the accumulation of points earned by making contributions, including both quantitative and qualitative components.

In the work presented at [36], Gutiérrez et al. analyze two different participation metrics in order to characterize the interaction between the members of a partially virtual community, concluding that the metrics used affect the community structure and the interaction patterns between its members.

Keeping in mind the limitations of the teaching context, UDPiler focuses mainly on the aspects of Challenge, Fellowship, Expression and Submission. We selected these particular aesthetical aspects because Vassileva [37] shows that the motivational community visualization design in an online community encourages social comparison and competition, which eventually results in an increased

participation on the part of the members. We believe that increasing the participation on a gamified platform will improve the learning performance of students on programming courses. In order to obtain empirical evidence of the improvement of learning performance, a quasi-experiment was, therefore, performed at the Diego Portales University, which is presented in the following section.

4 Study Research Method

The method chosen in order to carry out the current empirical research was a quasi-experiment, given that it was not possible to randomly assign the treatments to the subjects [38]. The quasi-experiment presented in this work was conducted with two groups of first-year Engineering students at the Diego Portales University (Chile) during the academic years 2014 and 2015. This experiment was run and is reported by following well-known guidelines [39], [40], [41].

4.1 Goal

The main goal of this quasi-experiment was to assess whether the use of a gamified platform improves the learning of C programming, in comparison to when a non-gamified platform is employed

We used the Goal-Question-Metric template [42], a commonly used method for the definition of experimental goals, in which the object of study, purpose, focus and the viewpoint of the measurement are clearly stated. The goal of this quasi-experiment can, therefore, be defined as follows:

“Analyze the use of different teaching methods
for the purpose of *evaluating them*
with regard to the performance of the students that learn C Programming
from the point of view of *researchers*
in the context of first-year students in the Engineering Faculty at the Diego Portales University in Chile”.

The gamified platform (used in 2015) corresponds to UDPiler (<https://udpiler.com>). UDPiler is a platform that allows different programming challenges to be tackled. UDPiler has 4 types of questions (challenges): multiple choice, completing or correcting a piece of code, codification to produce an expected output, and winning a mini game by means of coding. The questions in UDPiler are grouped by topic, and by the concepts in each topic. Each student that obtains a correct answer is given a medal and obtains some points, which are added to a rank on the programming course. The medals are images with a related content, such as an image of a Marvel superhero with his/her official (profile provided by the official Marvel API), a top YouTube video, a mini game, and so on. The complete mechanics of UDPiler can be found in Section 3.

Each student on the programming course carried out with UDPiler had to register on the platform in order to obtain a password that would enable him/her to use the tool. The lecturer gave classes to teach the contents, and provided the students with a set of exercises; moreover, the students used UDPiler whenever they wanted, to answer questions in the order that they wanted (without taking into account their difficulty), to win medals, videos, mini-games, to look at the medals and videos won previously, to see where they were located in the ranking, to use the compiler, or simply to go over the lecturer's lessons. The use of UDPiler was strictly optional, i.e., the students were not forced to use it nor did they have to go through UDPiler to complete graded homework. Several challenges were similar to exam questions, but not identical. For example, one UDPiler challenge requires the students to write a program. Given the three corner points of a triangle, the program must determinate whether it is equilateral, isosceles or scalene. The corresponding question in the exam was, however, to determine whether, given the four corner points of a square and the three points of a triangle, the triangle is inside the square.

The non-gamified platform corresponds to an online compiler (used in 2014), which is the traditional means employed to teach classes, when a teacher uses PowerPoint slides to present the contents of each lesson and to give exercises to the students. The students later employ a compiler by using a web interface to compile the code, which we refer to as an online compiler.

The online compiler came into being in order to make it easier for the students to do the programming course exercises, but they were not obliged to use it. In contrast to UDPiler, the online compiler does not present challenges related to the programming course topics, nor does it have features such as rewards for the students, mini-games, a ranking system, etc. In short, the online compiler does not have gamification elements, as UDPiler has.

4.2 Context

The programming course is compulsory for first-year Engineering students at the Diego Portales University. The students at this institution are enrolled on Computer Engineering, Industrial Engineering, Civil Engineering, and Foundation Engineering degrees. At this point, it is important to mention that the students must take a national exam called the PSU (University Selection Test) that evaluates the general competences that students must have to become university students in Chile. The scores required by those students that wish to study for engineering degrees are similar to the scores required to study engineering degrees at the Diego Portales University. More details on this exam and the score needed to study engineering at the Diego Portales University can be found in [43]. All the students have similar backgrounds, since they have obtained similar PSU scores and are in their first year at university, signifying that they have not previously undertaken

any programming courses. All the students enrolled on the programming course (from all the engineering degrees) participated in the quasi experiment, thus enabling us to have a large sample of subjects.

Three groups of subjects participated in the study:

- Non-Gam-2014: This first group, which in experimentation is usually called the “control group”, comprised 407 first-year students enrolled on the programming course in the Engineering Faculty at the Diego Portales University – Chile during the second semester of 2014. These students were enrolled on the programming course from August 2014 to December 2014.

The other two groups were made up of the 410 first-year students in the Engineering Faculty at the Diego Portales University – Chile during the first semester of 2015. These students were enrolled on the programming course from March 2015 to July 2015 and were divided into two subgroups according to their usage of UDPiler and the number of challenges solved correctly when using it:

- Gam-2015: This subgroup contained 267 students who performed at least 12 challenges correctly before the mid-term exam using UDPiler. This number was established by the course professors since, according to their expertise, it corresponds to the minimum number of challenges to be solved correctly if the usage of UDPiler is be considered as useful.
- Non-Gam-2015: This subgroup was formed of 143 students who performed less than 12 challenges correctly, including those who did not use UDPiler at all.

The experimental objects were the exams that the students have to sit when enrolled on the programming course. The exams were designed by the teaching staff of the programming course, and all the students enrolled on this course in a semester took the same exams. Each student had to take two exams, the details of which are shown below:

- Exam 1 consisted of three questions; Q1, Q2, and Q3, which each student had to answer in 1.5 hours. Q1 was related to variables (read/write from/to screen), data types, memory allocation, use of variables, and mathematical operators. Q2 was related to all the topics in Q1, plus control instructions, “if”, “else” and comparison operators. Q3 was related to all the topics in Q1 and Q2, plus cycles and the use of iterative instructions such as “for” and “while”.
- Exam 2 consisted of three questions; Q1, Q2, and Q3, which each student had to answer in 1.5 hours, as in the previous exam. Q1 was related to functions: parameters, creation, calls, return values, input and output functions, etc. Q2 was related to the topics in Q1, plus pointers, modifying values in memory, and passing parameters to functions as pointers to memory. Q3 was related to the topics presented in Q2, plus one-dimensional arrays, the algorithms required to go through arrays, methods with which to find minimum and maximum values, search and order methods, character arrays, strings, the functions used to

manage strings, and string arrays.

4.3 Variables

The independent variable was the method used to teach the C programming language, which we denominated as *Prog-Method*. This was a nominal variable with two values (treatments): Gamified (Gam) and Non-Gamified (Non-Gam).

The dependent variable was the *Learning Performance* of the students when learning the C programming language. We measured this dependent variable by defining the following measures:

- Mark 1: this corresponds to the mark obtained in an exam taken in the middle of the semester, called Exam 1 (see section 4.2).
- Mark 2: this corresponds to the mark obtained in an exam taken at the end of the semester, called Exam 2 (see section 4.2).

All these marks were calculated in a range between 10 (minimum) and 70 (maximum). At this point, it is important to mention that the UDPiler gamified platform has a module called ranking, which orders the scores obtained by the subjects when they solve challenges. These scores were employed to place the students in each of the 2015 subgroups.

4.4 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated on the basis of the goal presented and the definition of the measures defined for the dependent variable:

- H_0 : The students using the gamified platform will not obtain different marks to those obtained by the students using the non-gamified platform in the mid-semester (Mark 1) and end-of-semester exams (Mark 2).
- H_1 : $\neg H_0$

4.5 Design

The design of the quasi-experiment was a between-subject design. This means that we had two different groups of students, each of which performed similar tasks using one of the teaching techniques (the gamified platform or the non-gamified platform). Fig. 4 shows a schematic diagram of the design of the quasi-experiment.

Fig. 4. Design of the quasi-experiment

4.6 Tasks and materials

Both groups (Non-Gam-2014 and Gam-2015) had to take two tests, Exam 1 and Exam 2, during the semester. Passing the course depended on the marks that the subjects obtained in these exams. As these were taken in different academic years, it was not possible to use the same instrument for Exam 1 and Exam 2 during 2014 and 2015. Nevertheless, each exam evaluated the same contents and the questions for each topic had the same level of difficulty. In addition, all the students enrolled on the programming course took the same tests (at the same time) in 2014, and all the students enrolled on the programming course took the same tests (at the same time) in 2015.

The students were assigned the same time to answer each exam, i.e., 1.5 hours. The only difference was the use of the online non-gamified compiler or the UDPiler gamified platform when preparing for the exam. Exam 1 and Exam 2 were written exams that took place in the classroom. The *Learning Performance* was evaluated by comparing the grades obtained in the mid- and end-of-semester exams (Mark 1 and Mark 2), attained as explained previously.

Finally, a questionnaire consisting of 4 questions (Table 2) was given as an optional post-experiment task to those subjects who had used the gamified platform. Since answering the questionnaire was an optional task performed after the students had finished the programming course, it does not correspond to the number of students that used the gamified platform. Nevertheless, we handed it out in order to obtain qualitative information regarding the subjects and their perceptions of the use of UDPiler. The main goal of using this qualitative questionnaire was to obtain insights into the students' perceptions of their learning performance when using a gamified platform. Moreover, a blank space was provided with the objective of obtaining the subjects' comments or suggestions. This questionnaire was given to those subjects in the Gam-2015 group who wished to answer it.

Table 2. Questions in the post-experiment questionnaire

QQ1. What engineering degree are you studying?
QQ2. What was the most useful module of UDPiler for the learning process?
QQ3. Did UDPiler help you to obtain better results on the programming course?
QQ4. Do you consider that the level of difficulty when using UDPiler was low, medium, or high?

4.7 Analysis Procedure

The data analysis was carried out in the following steps [44]:

1. We first carried out a descriptive study of the measures of the dependent variable, i.e., Mark 1 and Mark 2, in order to obtain a general overview of the results.
2. We performed commonly-used normality and homogeneity statistical tests, i.e., Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Levene's tests, to determine the normality of the homogeneity of variances. These analyses were useful as regards determining which test would be suitable in the hypothesis contrast tests.
3. As the data were not normally distributed, we used Mann-Whitney's U test to contrast the experimental hypotheses. In all the statistical tests, we decided to accept a probability of 5% of committing a Type-I-Error.
4. We later considered the results obtained in the post-experiment questionnaire in order to both identify some of the subjects' characteristics and improve the UDPiler platform.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results obtained after the execution of this quasi-experiment. These results were statistically analyzed using SPSS v.24 [45].

5.1 Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics related to Mark 1 and Mark 2 (see Table 3) reveal that the grades obtained when using the gamified platform (Gam-2015) were higher than in the other cases.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for Mark1 and Mark2

	Prog-Method	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Mark 1	Non-Gam-2014	407	46.563	15.6990
	Gam-2015	267	55.555	12.7114
	Non-Gam-2015	143	50.406	14.6956
Mark 2	Non-Gam-2014	407	40.378	14.7188
	Gam-2015	267	49.109	12.6238
	Non-Gam-2015	143	48.175	14.3950

Fig. 5 shows the results obtained by the Non-Gam-2014 group and the Gam-2015 group. This figure shows the students' performance in terms of the marks obtained. In both cases, Mark 1 and Mark 2, an improvement in the learning performance can be observed for the Gam-2015 group with respect to the Non-Gam-2014 group.

Fig.5.Boxplot of the results obtained in Mark 1 and Mark 2 by both groups.

5.2 Testing hypotheses regarding mid-semester exams (H_0)

We decided to check the hypotheses twice, once by comparing the data obtained for the different years (Non-Gam-2014 vs. Gam-2015), and once more by comparing the performance of students in the same year (Gam-2015 vs. Non-Gam-2015). This double-checking of the hypotheses was carried out in order to strengthen the benefits of gamification.

In all cases, we applied the usual test employed to check data normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov), and we obtained that the values were not normally distributed. We consequently decided to use Mann-Whitney's U test to test the hypotheses.

With regard to the results obtained after comparing the Non-Gam-2014 and the Gam-2015 groups, Table 4 shows that the level of significance of the test is, for both variables, over 99.9%, signifying that the null hypothesis H_0 , which stated that students using the gamified platform would not obtain different marks to students using the non-gamified platform, can be rejected (as the level of significance is below the alpha value, which we set at 0.05).

Table 4. Results of the t-test for Mark 1 and Mark 2 (Non-Gam-2014 vs Gam-2015)

Variable	U	sig.
Mark 1	37818.0	<0.001
Mark 2	39705.5	<0.001

However, Table 5 shows that when comparing the results obtained by the Gam-2015 group with those of the Non-Gam-2015 group, the significance level of the test is over 99.9% only for Mark 1. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_0 can only be rejected in that case.

Table 5. Results of the t-test for Mark 1 and Mark 2 (Gam-2015 vs Non-Gam-2015)

Variable	U	sig.
Mark 1	15963.5	<0.001
Mark 2	19685.5	0.403

5.3 Analysis of post-experiment questionnaire

The post-experiment questionnaire was answered voluntarily by 66 subjects on all the engineering degrees taught in the Engineering Faculty at the Diego Portales University (see Fig. 6). These 66 students used the UDPiler gamified platform and answered the questionnaire after they finished the programming course. Since this activity was voluntary, it did not affect the marks obtained previously by the students; we believe that their answers were honest, since they were not afraid that their final result on the course would be affected. However, since the survey was performed after they finished the course, the students were on holiday and many of them did not return to the university to answer the questionnaire. Moreover, it is important to mention that there are more students on the Industrial Engineering and Computer Engineering degrees than on the Civil Engineering and Foundation Engineering degrees. Fig. 6 shows the lower participation in these last two degrees.

Fig.6. Answers to QQ1

According to the answers to question QQ2, which dealt with the most useful modules of UDPiler, the Top 3 modules are playbox, compiler and ranking (see Fig. 7). This question was formulated in order to define future improvements that could be made to the UDPiler components. It was surprising that the ranking module was in the top 3, even higher than the lessons. This could be explained by the ability of UDPiler to engage students and achieve competitiveness. It would appear that students attempt to attain a higher ranking in order to beat the other students, and to do so they need to play and obtain correct answers.

Fig.7. Answers to QQ2

With regard to the question concerning whether UDPiler helps them to improve their learning on the programming course, 19.7% of the subjects did not think that UDPiler helped them, but more than 80% of the subjects stated that UDPiler did

help them to obtain better results (see Fig. 8). Even though the subjects had not studied programming previously, they answered QQ3 by taking into account their previous learning experience in general. The results obtained regarding the perception that UDPiler helps to improve learning reinforces the statistical results obtained for *Learning Performance* (sections 5.1 and 5.2).

Fig.8. Answers to QQ3.

For QQ4, we carefully explained to the subjects that the level of difficulty is related to their perception of the difficulty of using UDPiler; it is not related to the difficulty of the exercises that they can do when using UDPiler. For QQ4, almost 60% of the subjects stated that the level of difficulty as regards using UDPiler was medium (see Fig. 9). Even though less than 10% of the subjects considered that the level of difficulty when using UDPiler was high, this perception suggests that UDPiler must be improved as regards its ease of use.

Fig.9. Level of difficulty when using UDPiler.

We identified the following relevant improvements that should be made to the UDPiler platform from the comments provided by the students: (1) the quantity of different correct answers for each question needs to be increased, (2) it is necessary to provide more difficult levels to users that are higher in the ranking, and (3) it would be a good idea to add challenges related to battles between subjects. These improvements to UDPiler would improve the skills needed by the students to master the use of this gamified platform and would enhance aspects concerning challenges and socialization.

5.4 Interpretation and discussion of results

The results shown in subsections 5.1 and 5.2 illustrate how the use of the gamified platform helped the students gain better academic results in each exam they took on the programming course. This improvement is statistically significant when comparing the groups from years 2014 and 2015 and it would, therefore, appear that that *Learning Performance* has been improved by using the gamified platform on programming courses. These findings seem to indicate that the UDPiler gamified platform could be an interesting tool to be considered on programming courses, especially in the quest to improve the *Learning Performance* of first-year students.

Moreover, when comparing the results obtained by the students in 2015, those who used UDPiler obtained better marks in their exams, with a statistically significant difference only in the mid-term exam, not in the final exam. Our interpretation of this is that students are currently very familiar with gaming, and probably much more so than with programming. This signifies that, when addressing programming for the first time, doing so using a gamified application helps them, especially in the earliest stages. That could be one reason why the difference is higher for the mid-term than for the end-of-semester exam.

The double-checking of the hypotheses, therefore, strengthens the benefits of using gamification in this context.

It is also interesting to note that the subjective perceptions of those students who used UDPiler pointed to several interesting facts which are, as far as we are concerned, in harmony with the results obtained in the data analysis. As stated in section 5.3, the students perceived UDPiler to be helpful (over 80%), although the tool could (and should) still be made easier to use.

Some other suggestions for improvement were received, which were related to the interaction between students, difficulty levels, etc., in addition to typical game features to be considered in further updates of the tool. We aware that the questionnaire could be improved by adding more questions related to perception of usefulness, ease of use, and intention to use UDPiler, and we shall, therefore, apply

the Technology Acceptance Method [46] in future replications of the quasi-experiment presented here.

Moreover, a recent research work [47] comprises an open enquiry as to what extent and how gamification supports retention and long-term learning. An additional insight of our study, which investigates the benefits of using the UDPiler gamified platform on a first-year course, is related to the rate of dropouts from the degree course itself. In 2014, the percentage of dropouts was 32%, while in 2015 it was down to 12%. This decrease in dropout rates suggests that we now have students who are more engaged in the degree, something which could very well be related to the use of the gamified platform. Nevertheless, further empirical studies are required to assess whether there is a correlation between the use of the gamified platform and the dropout rates.

Moreover, on the basis of our results, which demonstrate that there is an improvement in the learning performance of those students who use the gamified platform, we consider that the following research questions require further investigation:

- Which of the gamified elements are most influential as regards producing a better learning performance?
- Does the students' behavior as regards attending classes alter when they use the gamified platform?
- Is the students' intra-class behavior altered when they socialize the ranking obtained in UDPiler?
- Is there a correlation between the marks obtained by each student and the time spent using UDPiler?
- Why do students not solve the challenges using clans?
- Do each student's personal characteristics (such as gender, place born, and previous school) affect the use of the gamified platform?
- Is it possible to take into account each student's profile in order to recommend challenges related to the weak parts of their knowledge?

5.5 Threats to Validity

In this section, we discuss the threats to validity that could affect the validity of our results, focusing our attention on the threats to construct, internal, external and conclusion validity [41]:

- **External validity:** External validity refers to the extent to which the results can be generalized to other situations and people. But we are conscious that, in our case, global generalization is not possible, particularly as human beings have taken part in the experimentation. The results could, therefore, be valid in similar contexts, such as C programming courses during first-year of Computer Science degrees. With regard to the representativeness of the materials used, all

the experimental materials were academic exams (see section 4.6). The experience and professionalism of the teaching staff involved has, in our opinion, alleviated any possible lack of quality or objectivity when creating these materials. We are aware that the exams used were performed in different academic years and were, therefore, different. This might have led to a different complexity but, as previously stated, the lecturer in charge of the final review of the exams is one of the authors of this work and particular attention was, therefore, paid to creating exams with a similar level of complexity. Some examples of these exams can be found at (<https://udpil.com>). The generalization to other populations of students (e.g. cohorts with different levels of motivation, or different educational backgrounds, different programming languages, etc.), is worthy of future experimentation.

- **Internal validity:** The intention of internal validity is to establish a causal relationship between treatments and outcome, i.e., the capability of stating that the outcome obtained has been produced by the treatments. One possible threat to this kind of validity is that the subjects were assigned to one group or another depending on the academic year in which they took the programming course. Our experience as lecturers indicates that there is normally no significant difference between the backgrounds of two consecutive academic years. Another possible threat is that the subjects could have attended programming classes at secondary school, signifying that the results could have been threatened by these subjects. However, this threat appears to be just as probable for all groups of subjects (Non-Gam-2014, Non-Gam-2015 and Gam-2015) and we, therefore, assume that there should be no difference in the results obtained in the reported quasi-experiment.
- **Construct validity:** Construct validity is concerned with the capability of relating the treatments used to the *cause*, and the outcome obtained to the *effect*. In our case, the measures used to provide values for the variables were based on the evaluation of exams, as has been done for several years, so we believe that the evaluation process can be considered suitable. Moreover, the dependent variable *Learning Performance* might have been affected by the teaching staff on the programming courses and the pedagogical methods used by these professors. In order to avoid this possible threat, the teaching staff were the same people throughout the data collection period (academic years 2014 and 2015), signifying that the pedagogical methods used by each professor will probably have affected the learning effectiveness in both cases (using the gamified platform and not using it). Nevertheless, in order to mitigate this threat, all the exams were created by a lecturer who has coordinated all the programming teaching staff for more than 5 years; this individual is also one of the authors of the present work. Another possible threat might be focusing the improvement in the performance of the students on the use of a gamified

platform in the second academic year only. We are also aware that a gamified environment can be more motivating for students, which might lead to more time spent practicing, doing exercises, etc., and thus a better grade in exams. Non-gamified elements, e.g. the use of forums or even the constantly-improving experience of the professors, might simultaneously also have affected the improvement in the performance.

- **Conclusion validity:** Conclusion validity concerns the data collection, the reliability of the measurement, and the validity of the statistical tests, all or any of which might affect the ability to draw a correct conclusion. In order to avoid possible threats related to data collection procedures, the data were collected by two of the authors of this work from the educational information system at the Diego Portales University, which stores all the marks obtained by the students enrolled at this university. Statistical tests were used to reject the null hypotheses, fulfilling all the requirements needed to do so, signifying that the validity of the results obtained is acceptable. With regard to the statistical power required to accept these results, the number of experimental subjects was sufficiently large for us to achieve a strong and acceptable statistical power in these tests.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper contributes to the empirical body of knowledge concerning the benefits of gamification in computing education. We focused on the improvements in the students' learning when they used a gamified platform on a first-year programming course, which is a fundamental course that computing students need to take in order to acquire programming skills. Our work goes further than that which is related to it, in which gamification when applied to programming courses has been studied by considering merely the importance of the use of a single gamification element (such as badges), rather than learning performance. The contribution of this paper is specifically to present a quasi-experiment that was undertaken to gather empirical evidence on the beneficial effects of gamification on the learning process on programming courses studied in the first-year of the Engineering degrees at the Diego Portales University and to present an open-source gamified platform that can be used on programming courses by other universities.

The quasi-experiment was performed with a large sample of first-year students. The results show that gamification is, to some extent, effective as regards improving the process of learning the C programming language, since the students using the gamified platform obtained higher grades than those using traditional teaching with a non-gamified compiler. This contribution may be useful for academics who are seeking new techniques with which to teach programming courses. It may also be of use to researchers who are on the look-out for evidence regarding gamified

platforms because they seek to carry out more research into requirements, types of challenges, reward systems, etc.

UDPiler has recently been extended in order to enable gamification to be applied to other first-year engineering modules, such as algebra and calculus. These modules have been chosen because many students do not have sufficient logical and mathematical knowledge, and we have observed that this kind of knowledge is very important when learning programming skills. Furthermore, additional further work will focus on making improvements to the UDPiler gamified platform. These are related to adding functionality to the gamified platform, recording how much time each student spends on the platform, along with registering the amount of time that the students are inactive in each session, adding new reward videos and implementing the improvements identified in the post-experiment questionnaire.

Despite the encouraging results obtained in this first quasi-experiment, we are aware that replication is needed to corroborate and strengthen the findings obtained. There is also a need to collect qualitative data concerning the perception of the use of the platform, such as how easy it is to use, intention to use the platform, etc. This will be our immediate further work, since we are planning to replicate this quasi-experiment in 2018. We shall, however, make slight modifications to its design, signifying that the new version of UDPiler will be used to conduct the replication. In this new version, we will collect gender data, age data, language data, and the previous knowledge of the students that will be using the gamified platform, in order to analyze whether there are any differences in their learning performance. Moreover, we plan to investigate the correlation that could exist between the use of the gamified platform and the dropout rates. As a long-term research work, we also plan to go a step further, by investigating whether or not the kind of gamified elements (mechanics, dynamics and aesthetics) used have any influence on the students' performance, the influence of the gamified platform on the students' attendance behavior and whether it is possible to use a recommended system to strength each student's weak knowledge.

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